

THE USE OF COOPERATIVE LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TEACHING OF CRIMINAL LAW

Khamrakulov Zafarjon Yigitalievich

Senior lecturer of Kokand State pedagogical institute,

Gmail: zafarjonxamraqulov@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7642169>

Abstract

The article covers the issues of using collaborative learning technologies in the teaching of criminal law. Also, the importance of such technologies in pedagogical education is revealed.

Key words: criminal law, cooperative education, pedagogy, technology.

Resolution No. PQ-4623 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 27, 2020 "On measures to further develop the field of pedagogical education" states "Improving the quality of education, training competitive personnel, scientific and innovative activities by ensuring the harmony of education, science and production in the field effective organization, ensuring the solid integration of modern information and communication and educational technologies, ultimately creating additional conditions for the continuous development of the professional skills of pedagogues; Priorities such as "increasing the efficiency of processes of formation of modern pedagogic personnel with high culture, practical professional skills, who have thoroughly mastered education, teaching methods and evaluation criteria" have been defined. These areas impose great tasks on pedagogues and other employees of the education sector[1].

Major changes in education are also directly related to higher education. The development of future specialists in the field of pedagogy into personnel with high moral qualities, being honest, kind to young people, fair, and conscientious, as well as having competence corresponding to the levels of modern education and training requirements, is related to the level of training in higher education.

Most of the issues studied in criminal law require the use of cooperative learning technologies. This technology is good for students to improve their knowledge in teams, small groups and in pairs, and identify institutional attributes and substances together. This is achieved by organizing students' relations based on cooperation, establishing professional and moral-spiritual unity between them.

Using the method of "Research in a small group" on criminal law, students are presented with the following assignment:

Task 1.

Give examples of guilt and clauses in it?

Guilt is a person's mental attitude towards the committed socially dangerous act and its consequences. Chapter 5 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes legal norms for forms of guilt, which can be expressed in the above scheme. Using it, students work together on the basis of cooperative education technology.

Task 2.

Describe the types and forms of participation in crime.

Participation in crime "two or more persons participating together in the commission of an intentional crime is considered participation." This legal institution has its own types and forms. Also, in Articles 30-31, the scope of responsibility for participation in the commission of a crime and issues of relevance allow a deeper understanding of the nature of this institution. It is desirable for students to learn these elements from Chapter 7 of the Criminal Code.

In cooperative education, it is advisable to use not only the organization of tasks, but also the methods of tests and basic outlines. It is appropriate to use the method of "work in small groups" in the collaborative technology of criminal law, in which students are united in groups of 4-5 people. The task is carried out in cooperation between them.

Based on the conducted experiments and scientific researches, it became clear that it is appropriate to expand the possibilities of using new innovative technologies in the teaching of criminal law in pedagogical education. Not limited to this, it is necessary to enrich the subjects of the science program on the use of innovative technologies in pedagogical activities in the teaching of criminal law. In addition, in order to improve the use of innovative technologies in the teaching of criminal law, it is necessary to include pedagogical issues related to the field in the topics of coursework and graduate qualifications.

As a result of active learning methods, the centralizing influence of the teacher weakens, and the activity of the audience increases. In the teaching of criminal law, consideration of complex and controversial social issues based on

conversation is one of the main methods of legal education. The extensive use of the interview method in lectures and seminar sessions plays an important role in the completion of any technology.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2020 йил 27 февралдаги “Педагогик таълим соҳасини янада ривожлантириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПҚ-4623-сон Қарори. – Т.: Қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси, 28.02.2020 й., 07/20/4623/0220-сон.
2. Yigitalievich K. Z. FUNDAMENTALS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS OF LAW PEDAGOGICS //Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development. – 2022. – Т. 10. – С. 154-160.
3. Yigitalievich, Khamrakulov Zafarjon. "DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'COMPETENCE IN THE USE OF LEGAL DOCUMENTS." Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal 10.12 (2022): 729-733.
4. Khamrakulov Z. Y. Philosophical and historical basis of the idea of prosperity //Asian Journal Of Multidimensional Research. – 2021. – Т. 10. – №. 6. – С. 357-363.
5. Yigitalievich K. Z. Increasing Legal Culture Of Students By Improving The Teaching Of Criminal Law //Czech Journal of Multidisciplinary Innovations. – 2022. – Т. 12. – С. 38-42.
6. Khamrakulov Z. PROBLEMS OF INCREASING LEGAL INFORMATION AND LEGAL LITERACY OF YOUTH //Models and methods in modern science. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 16. – С. 4-7.

